

Detection of physical interactions between Cor proteins using the bacterial two hybrid system (BACTH)

Principle

The BACTH assay is dependent upon the functional reconstitution of the *Bordetella pertussis* adenylate cyclase T18 and T25 sub-domains by two interacting partners.

Karimova, G., Pidoux, J., Ullmann, A. and Ladant, D. (1998) A bacterial two-hybrid system based on a reconstituted signal transduction pathway. Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A. 95, 5752–5756 CrossRef PubMed

Proteins A and B are genetically fused to the T18 and T25 fragments (Figure 1). Interaction between protein A and B leads to cAMP synthesis which can be easily detected in *E. coli cya* cells. This system allows to detect interactions occurring in the cytosol, in the cytoplasmic membrane and even in the periplasm

Figure 1. Scheme describing the BACTH system.

This system is based on the reconstitution of the adenylate cyclase (*Cya*) activity of *Bordetella pertussis* in *Escherichia coli*, thanks to the interaction of its two domains T18 and T25. When these two fragments are fused to two interacting proteins, A and B, the adenylate cyclase activity is restored which induces a production of cyclic AMP. cAMP then activates transcription of the lactose operon, in particular the *lacZ* gene which encodes the beta-galactosidase enzyme. It is thus possible to quantify the interaction by measuring the beta-galactosidase activity thanks to a colorimetric assay using ONPG as a substrate of beta galactosidase. In parallel, the interaction can be visualized on a petri dish containing X gal, another substrate of beta-galactosidase.

OBJECTIVES

Mg²⁺ efflux is not well understood in *Salmonella* Typhimurium and proteins CorB, CorC and CorD could play this function *via* CorA (as energy source or ion sensor). Gibson MM, Bagga DA, Miller CG, Maguire ME. Magnesium transport in *Salmonella typhimurium*: the influence of new mutations conferring Co²⁺ resistance on the CorA Mg²⁺ transport system. Molecular microbiology. 1991;5(11):2753-62.

The *Salmonella* CorB, CorC and CorD proteins have not been characterized since 1991. **The main objective** of the present study was to find out potential physical interactions between CorA, CorB(=YfjD), CorC(=YbeX) and CorD(=ApaG). By affinity capture-MS studies in *E. coli*,

physical interactions between YbeX and either CorA or NuoA have been suspected. NuoA (NADH-quinone oxidoreductase subunit A) is a component of the plasma membrane respiratory chain complex. [Global landscape of cell envelope protein complexes in *Escherichia coli*. Nat. Biotechnol. Nov. 27, 2017 PubMed ID: 29176613.](#) **A second objective** of the present study was thus to check potential physical interactions between YbeX(CorC) and NuoA.

METHODS

The BATCH experiments were carried out according to the protocol described in Karimova *et al.* 1998. Cells of the *E. coli* DHT1 strain (a *cyo* mutant) were co-transformed with plasmids derived from the vectors pUT18, pUT18C, pKT25 and pKNT25 allowing the expression of proteins of interest fused to the T18 or T25 fragments of adenylate cyclase. Three colonies of each of the recombinant strains were cultured in LB liquid medium. The cultures obtained after 18 h were used to measure beta-galactosidase activity in order to quantify a potential interaction between the proteins of interest (Figure 3). In parallel, 5 µl of each of the cultures were spotted on LB plate containing X-gal in order to visualize potential interactions, as indicated by a blue color (Figure 2).

Karimova, G., Pidoux, J., Ullmann, A. and Ladant, D. (1998) A bacterial two-hybrid system based on a reconstituted signal transduction pathway. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 95, 5752–5756 [CrossRef PubMed](#)

Degree of protein interaction can be quantified by measuring levels of beta-galactosidase activity according to a protocol described by Miller.

Miller, J. H. (1972) *Experiments in Molecular Genetics*. Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press, Cold Spring Harbor.

MATERIAL

The Cor proteins

Magnesium/nickel/cobalt transporter CorA encoded by STM14_4754

CorC soluble protein encoded by *ybeX* (STM14_0776)

CorB membrane protein encoded by *yffD* (STM14_3284)

Putative CorD soluble protein encoded by *apaG* (STM14_0108)

Plasmids constructed

ATCC14028 *ybeX=corC*

- 1) PCR fragment (primers *ybeX*2H-SD-pst and *ybeX*pUT18-Kpn-BIS) cloned into pUT18 (PstI-KpnI). Clone H667 (sequence was checked)
- 2) PCR fragment (primers *ybeX*2H Xba et *ybeX*pUT18C-Kpn) cloned into pUT18C (XbaI-KpnI). Clone H664 (sequence was checked)
- 3) *corC* fragment cloned in pUT18C (H664) was cloned into pKT25 (XbaI-KpnI). Clone H690 (sequence was checked)
- 4) *corC* fragment cloned in pUT18 (H667) was cloned into pKNT25 (Pst-KpnI). Clones H693 and H694 (sequence was checked)

ATCC14028 *apaG=corD*

- 1) PCR fragment (primers *apaG* 2H SD Pst and *apaG* 2H Eco) cloned into pUT18 (PstI-EcoRI). Clone H634 (sequence was checked)
- 2) PCR fragment (primers *apaG*2H xba and *apaG* 2H Kpn) cloned into pUT18C (XbaI-KpnI). Clone H668 (sequence was checked)
- 3) *apaG* fragment cloned in pUT18C (H668) was cloned into pKT25 (XbaI-KpnI). Clones H707 and H708 (sequence was checked)
- 4) *apaG* fragment cloned in pUT18 (H634) was cloned into pKNT25 (PstI-EcoRI). Clone H697 (sequence was checked)

ATCC14028 *yfjD=corB*

yfjD= STM14_3284

- 1) PCR fragment (primers *yfjD* 2H SD Pst and *yfjD* pUT18 Eco) cloned into pUT18 (PstI-EcoRI). Clone H635 (sequence was checked)
- 2) PCR fragment (primers *yfjD*2H xba et *yfjD* pUT18C Eco) cloned into pUT18C (XbaI-EcoRI). Clone H575 (sequence was checked)
- 3) *apaG* fragment cloned in pUT18C (H575) was cloned into pKT25 (XbaI-EcoRI). Clones H822 and H823 (sequence was checked)
- 4) *apaG* fragment cloned in pUT18 (H635) was cloned into pKNT25 (PstI-EcoRI). Clone H700 (sequence was checked)

yfjD with 5' elongated (YfjD with N-ter elongated)

- 1) PCR fragment (primers *yfjD*long-2H-SD-Pst and *yfjD*-pUT18-Eco) cloned into pUT18 (PstI-EcoRI). Clone H820 (sequence was checked)
- 2) PCR fragment (primers *yfjD*long-2H-Xba and *yfjD*-pUT18C-Eco) cloned into pUT18C (XbaI-EcoRI). Clones H818 and H819 (sequence was checked)
- 3) *yfjD* fragment cloned in pUT18C (H818) was cloned into pKT25 (XbaI-EcoRI). Clone H836 (sequence was checked)
- 4) *yfjD* fragment cloned in pUT18 (H820) was cloned into pKNT25 (PstI-EcoRI). Clone H836 (sequence was checked)

ATCC14028 *corA*

- 1) *corA* PCR fragment (primers CorA-Xba and CorA-Kpn) cloned into pKT25 (Xba-KpnI). Clone H835 (sequence was checked)
- 2) *corA* PCR fragment (primers CorA-Xba and CorA-Kpn) cloned into pUT18C (XbaI-KpnI). Clone H824 (sequence was checked)
- 3) *corA* PCR fragment (primers *corA*-SD-Pst and *corA* -Eco) cloned into pUT18 (PstI-EcoRI) → clones H695 and H696 (sequence was checked) cloned into pKNT25 (PstI-EcoRI) → clones H703 and H704 (sequence was checked)

ATCC14028 *nuoA*

- 1) PCR fragment (primers NuoA-SD-Pst and NuoA-Eco) cloned into pUT18 (PstI-EcoRI). Clones H675, H677, H678 (sequence was checked)
- 2) PCR fragment (primers NuoA-Xba and NuoA-Kpn) cloned into pUT18C (XbaI-KpnI). Clones H672, H673, H674 (sequence was checked)
- 3) *nuoA* fragment cloned in pUT18C was cloned into pKT25 (XbaI-KpnI). Clone H686 (sequence was checked)
- 4) *nuoA* fragment cloned in pUT18 was cloned into pKNT25 (Eco Pst). Clones H691 and H692 (sequence was checked)

PRIMERS USED

PRIMERS *yfjD*

yfjD-2H-SD-Pst

CATGCCTGCAGGTGAGAACTGGAATGATGACGCTAAACCGTTACCGT

yfjD-pUT18-Eco

TCGATGAATTCGACTCCGCCACACTCTCGCGCAGCGGTTTTACCGGTACA

YfjD-2H-Xba

TCGACTCTAGAGATGACGCTAAACCGTTACCGTTTACGCCATATGGCGA

YfjD-pUT18C-Eco

CGATGAATTCTTACTCCGCCCACTCTCGCGCAGCGGTTTTACCGGTA

yfjDlong-2H-Xba

TCGACTCTAGAGATGGTGGTCATCTCGGCCTATTTTTCCGGT

yfjDlong-2H-SD-Pst

CATGCCTGCAGGTGAATTATCATATTAATCATCATGGTGGTCATCT

PRIMERS YbeX

YbeX-2H-SD-Pst

CATGCCTGCAGGTGACATGAGAACCATACGACGCCATGAGCGACGACAATTCA

YbeX-pUT18-Kpn

TCGACGGTACCCGTTCGTCCAGTTTTGGCTGGGGCGAGTCATCCGGGATCCT

YbeX-2H-Xba

TCGACTCTAGAGATGAGCGACGACAATTCACACAGTAGTGACACAGTA

YbeX-pUT18C-Kpn

AGCTCGGTACCTTATTCGTCCAGTTTTGGCTGGGGCGAGTCATCCGGGAT

YbeX-pUT18-Kpn BIS

AGCTCGGTACCCGTTCGTCCAGTTTTGGCTGGGGCGAGTCATCCGGGATCCT

PRIMERS ApaG

ApaG-2H-SD-Pst

CATGCCTGCAGGTGAGCCTTTGAAGGAGAGTTAAACATGATCAATTCGCCCAGA

ApaG-2H-Eco

TCGATGAATTTCGAGTGAATGAGTGTAGGGACGGCGAGTCGAAACACGGGGA

ApaG-2H-Xba

TCGACTCTAGAGATGATCAATTCGCCCAGAGTGTGTATTCAGGTGCAAAGCGT

ApaG-2H-Kpn

AGCTCGGTACCTTAGTGAATGAGTGTAGGGACGGCGAGTCGAAACACGGGGA

PRIMERS CorA

CorA-Xba

CGACTCTAGAGATGCTGAGCGCATTTCAACTGGAA

CorA-Kpn
AGCTCGGTACCTTACAGCCAGTTCTTGCGCTTAAAGTA

corA-SD-Pst
5'-CATGCC/TGC/AGG/TGACGCATTGGGAGTCCCGGTCATGCTGAGCGCATTCA

corA-Eco
5'-TCGA/TGA/ATT/CGA/CAGCCAGTTCTTGCGCTTAAAGTACAAATACGGCG

PRIMERS NuoA

nuoA-Xba
5'-TCGACTCTAGAGATGagtatgtcaacatccactgaagtcacgct

nuoA-Kpn
5'-AGCTCGGTACCTTAgcgttgacgattagcgatactgttcgt

NuoA-SD-Pst
5'-CATGCCTGCAGGTGATTGATGAGTAAGCAATGAGTATGTCAACATCCA

NuoA-Eco
5'-TCGATGAATTCGAGCGTTGACGATTAGCGATACTGTTTCGT

RESULTS

The topology of the fusion protein must be taken into account since the test will be valid only if the T18 and T25 fragments are located in the cytoplasm. Two Cor proteins; CorA and YfjD/CorB are located in the inner membrane and thus contain transmembrane fragments. We have fused T18 and T25 at the cytoplasmic N-terminus of CorA. For YfjD, CorC and ApaG the proteins were fused to T18 and T25 at both ends.

Cells of DHT1, a *cya* mutant of *E. coli*, were co-transformed with the recombinant plasmids indicated and derived from the vectors pUT18, pUT18C pKT25 and pKNT25 (Figures 2 and 3). Three colonies of each of the recombinant strains were cultured for 18 hours in LB liquid medium at 30°C. Beta-galactosidase activity was measured for each of the cultures (Figure 2). Empty vectors were used as negative controls. The positive control is based on the known interaction between the stress sigma factor of RNA polymerase (RpoS/ σ^S) and the Crl protein (Monteil *et al* 2010). It corresponds to *E. coli* DHT1 containing plasmids expressing T18-Crl and RpoS-T25 fusions (Monteil *et al* 2010). In parallel, 5 μ l of each of the cultures were spotted on LB plates containing Xgal and the appropriate antibiotics (Figure 3). Plates were incubated for 24 hours at 30°C and then photographed. A blue color is an indicator of beta-galactosidase activity and therefore of an interaction between the proteins tested.

Monteil V, Kolb A, D'Alayer J, Beguin P, Norel F. Identification of conserved amino acids residues of the *Salmonella* σ^S chaperone Crl involved in Crl- σ^S interactions. *J Bacteriol.* 2010, 192(4) : 1075-87.

- Our data confirmed that CorA interacts with itself (Figures 2 and 3), which is expected since CorA is a homopentamer.

Moreover altogether our results (Figures 2 and 3) suggest that :

- CorB/YfjD interacts with itself, forming at least one dimer
- CorC/YbeX interacts with itself, forming at least one dimer
- **YfjD interacts with both CorC/YbeX and CorA.**
- ApaG protein interacts with itself, forming at least one dimer but does not seem to interact with the other Cor proteins tested (data not shown).
- No significant interaction was detected between YbeX/CorC and NuoA using the BACTH system (data not shown).

Figure 2. Highlighting potential interactions between Cor proteins in the BACTH system. The histograms represent the means of beta-galactosidase activities obtained for the three biological replicates and bars represent the standard errors of the means.

Figure 3. Visualization on LB X-gal of the beta-galactosidase activity of cultures used to quantify potential interactions between Cor proteins in the BACTH system (Figure 2).